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Occupational Stress and Burnout among Police Constables

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Abstract

Policing is a stressful occupation, which impairs police Constables' physical/mental health and elicits burnout, aggressive behaviors and suicide. Resilience and coping facilitate the management of job stress policing, which can be operational or organizational. All these constructs are associated, and they must be assessed by instruments sensitive to policing idiosyncrasies. This study aims to identify operational and organizational stress, burnout, resilient coping and coping strategies among police officers. A cross-sectional study, with questionnaires (Burnout Inventory by K. S. Mishra (2012), Occupational Stress Index by A.P. Singh & A.K. Srivastava, (1982)), collected data of 50 police Constables and revealed a structure with two factors (poor management and lack of resources, and responsibilities and burden). Considering cut-off points, 88.4% police Constables presented high operational stress, 87.2% high organizational stress, 10.9% critical values for burnout and preferring task-orientated than emotion and avoidance coping. Some differences were found according to gender, age and job experience. Job stress and burnout correlated negatively with resilient coping, enthusiasm towards job and task-orientated coping. Results reinforce the importance to invest on police Constables' occupational health.

Keywords: *Burnout Inventory, Occupational Stress.*

1: Introduction

POLICE

Policing has been described as one of the most challenging, stressful, health threatening and psychologically dangerous jobs in the world. Their work is associated with danger, bureaucracy, politics and tense community relations. Police are defined as those nonmilitary individuals or organizations who are given the general right by government to use coercive force to enforce the law and whose primary purpose is to respond to problems of individual and group conflict that involve illegal behavior. The police role, and what is considered to be appropriate activity and behavior, is determined by legal requirements, the police organization, and the community.

Police work is seems not a job but a calling by 24x7. A police officer faces physical dangers on a daily basis and stress for which he or she is not trained to deal with. He also assets that the police officer has to face scrutiny from the community and his/her own peers on a daily basis. Nowadays, Hollywood & Bollywood action packed movies also glamorizes police work, making the police officers to be seen as a hero- a tough character with no fear and who can experience trauma and violence without suffering any ill effects.

Officers in the field struggle with constantly changing situations, and routine calls which can go bad quickly. They also pursue dangerous and sometimes desperate criminals who make poor decisions out of panic. A police officer must be able to rapidly assess a situation and make sound choices which will benefit the community, using the tools at his or her disposal, which can range from riot gear to ticket books. Responding to high-risk calls demands an elevated level of alertness, engagement in the moment, quick thinking and the capacity to perform well under high stress. This is not unlike what a professional athlete experiences during competition. However, there is often a long-term cost of being able to perform in these high-demand situations: failure to survive emotionally. Many officers who begin their careers with unbridled enthusiasm end up, over the course of their careers, suffering problems in both their personal lives and their long-term relationships with their department. Is there a connection between the type of officer who, early in his career, likes the emotional intensity offered by police work and the officer who may experience personal and professional difficulty as their career progresses? The answer is yes, and here is why.

MAJOR MENTAL HEALTH RELATED PROBLEMS FACED BY OUR POLICE PERSONNEL

Sources of stress

Researches indicates that people within certain occupations, such as accountants, air traffic controllers, lawyers, physicians, and police officials experience a higher than average amount of stress and the level of stress vary by job assignment. Colwell confirms this notion indicating that police work tends to impose a higher degree of stress and a multiplicity of stressful situations on the individual than do most other professions. After a review of literature available on mental health problems associated with police work, the following sources have been identified. This information is gathered from several magazines, newspapers, journal articles and reflecting the sources of stressors, have been categorized as follows:

Stress among policemen would manifest in the form of fatigue, depression, inability to concentrate and impulsive behavior. These danger signals are quite common among the traffic policemen and patrolling police whose nature of work is such that they hardly can control their temper.

People normally complain that policemen are rude and highhanded, but what they fail to see are the extreme conditions under which they lead their lives. A number of studies were carried out in different parts of the world for understanding the level of stress among police personnel.

In a recently conducted study among the West Bengal Police Officers revealed that 42 and 12% of the West Bengal Police Officers were suffering from moderate and high psychological stress respectively. Further analysis of data revealed that the main areas of stress included un-profitability (32%), role overload (74%), role conflict (50%), powerlessness (28%), role ambiguity (36%), unreasonable group and political pressure (58%), intrinsic impoverishment (32%) and under participation (60%). Findings suggest that special attention is required for taking need-based measures for each of the above areas of stress for unburdening the level of stress among West Bengal Police Officers [8]. In another study carried out by Kolkata Traffic Police Officers, found that the main causes of stress were inadequate rest, no leave, and abstaining from social occasions and excessive work pressure.

- Green carried out a study among Police Officers with a view to ascertaining whether the Police Officers had severe post-traumatic stress disorders (PTSD) than in civilians. No significant differences were found,

although there was a tendency for higher use of alcohol and to try not to think about the trauma

- The magnitude and dimensions of a policeman's organizational stress has been totally overlooked so far in India. In Punjab, Kashmir and North Eastern regions, CRPF personnel remain under constant threats of injury or death or repeated narrow escapes. A number of psychological and interpersonal factors contribute to the overall stress load experienced by the CRPF personnel such as a reduction in personal freedom, separation from home and loved ones, constant fear and anxiety and unpredictability of the operational combat situation. Police personnel undergo intense stress, when they see their colleagues and co-workers injured or killed during performance of duties. Police personnel, who are the helpless witnesses of the ghastly scenes of tens of people killed in a terrorist shootout in a train etc. can never forget the ghastly sight.
- Indian policemen are constantly facing rapid social changes such as breakup of joint family system, which gave security, increasing mental conflicts, and social disorders and social changes have brought in their wake a number of stresses for them. Police in India, particularly, after independence, generally suffer from serious chronic stress due to job-ambiguity, conflicting values, negative police image and job overload. Sometime life threatening situations create serious stress among police personnel particularly when they have a feeling of economic insecurity for their families and dependents.
- Police officials are generally never paid nearly what they should be. Levinson asserts that mental health workers and policemen who work under severe pressure in people-orientated jobs for long periods of time with little support and limited gains are among the prime victims of burnout. Sewell confirms that police officials receive poor salaries. Salary increases, have not been sufficient because there are other increases as well such as medical aids, pension contributions and taxes. "Benefits such as subsidized vehicles and cell phones are not allotted to officials with lower ranks or middle management and it seems as if these people live from hand to mouth. As a result of a low salary, many employees in government departments are moonlighting in order to generate an additional income. This is a very real cause of corruption.
- According to Van Zyl once employees have been disadvantaged via restructuring, a promotional process or any other such occurrence, and the injustice is not rectified at a later stage, they may develop a permanent feeling of being the victim of the processes and procedures within the organization.
- According to Geldenhuys most police officials who have to kill a suspect in the line of duty experience a great deal of conflicting emotions like guilt even if

they were completely justified in using violence. They experience a great deal of mental trauma and depression due to the fact that they have actually taken the life of another human being. Although the person shot was a criminal, somewhere out there is a family who has lost a loved one. There is nothing glamorous about killing another human being. This can have devastating consequences that erode the emotional well-being of any person, even that of a seasoned police official.

According to Geldenhuys police officials are trained to hide their emotions, right from day one at the Police Training College. They see emotions as getting in the way of the job they are performing. Emotions are suppressed daily for years. The stress takes its toll either quickly or slowly and police officials experience Post-Traumatic Stress Disorders (PTSD). Every time a police official is called to a crime scene, the adrenalin pumps. Police are aware that their lives are in danger. Also, they work an average of 10 hours a day during which time they attend to cases like housebreaking, domestic violence, armed robbery, rape, hit and run, murder or suicide.

After the night shift, the chances are good that they must be in court the next day to testify about a case that took place weeks, months or even years ago. Should there be any time left to rest, they try to rest for a while before the sun sets and they have to report on duty for the night shift again.

MacClean (cited in Corelli) asserts that alcohol abuse among policemen is more than the norm because of the type of work that they do, their superman mentality, the macho image that they feel they have to protect and to handle the pressures of the job, they engage in their favourite pastime which is drinking.

Tripathi, Naidu, Thapa and Biswas have done a project on 'Stress, Health and Performance: A study of Police Organization in Uttar Pradesh'. They found that

(a) The constables had significantly higher suicidal tendency compared to the head constables, sub-inspectors and the inspectors. The deputy SPs did not differ from any other groups.

(b) The constables and head constables experienced significantly greater degree of daily hassles compared to the other groups and the inspectors experienced the least degree of daily hassles

(c) The constables were significantly more depressed than any other groups and the deputy SPs were the least depressed group

(d) Suicide was negatively associated with grant of leave and support of officers means, those who did not get leave during times of emergency and failed to get support from higher officers were more likely to commit suicide.

(e) Depression was significantly associated with low degree of just reward in the organization, low satisfaction with promotion procedures, low chances

of getting leave, lower authority and low support from officers. It was positively related with dissatisfaction with transfer procedures and conflict. It is high time we noticed the above mentioned alarming trends of police behavior and conducted proper study of police stress in India. There is a need for growing organizational sensitivity to the problem of stress in police in India. There are only a few studies on the stress of police personnel and there is an imperative need for more field studies. As a participant observer, I found that police job frequently leads to mental stagnation, psychological fatigue, lop-sided development of personality, and constantly stressful challenges endangering personal safety and life. Pessimism, neuroticism and cynicism were significantly related with job-stress in police. Young officers, particularly feel more stress and feel constantly a sense of injustice when job-demands are not commensurate with the administrative and organizational support. Constables and Head Constables have serious stress when they find inadequate training; hostile working environment and long hours of work are all contributing adverse effect on their health and personality.

According to Schaefer law enforcement has traditionally been referred to as an occupation that leads to a variety of stress related maladies such as hypertension, cardiovascular irregularities, and gastrointestinal disorders. According to Finn police work is widely considered to be among the most stressful occupations. It is associated with high rates of divorce, alcoholism, suicide and other emotional and health problems. Geldenhuys claims that police do not receive the praise, glory and appreciation that they deserve. Roosendaal concurs, saying that a police official has one of the most thankless jobs. To some of middle and lower rank, respect and appreciation for their work is just a dream. Found following important factors that emerges in his thematic content analysis of exploring the construct of police job's stressors i.e. nature of duty, lack of support, external pressure (political pressure), feeling of biasness, lack of freedom, lack of infrastructure, and working conditions. Further, police job's stressors were negatively related to quality of life, job performance, quality of work life, and personal life of police personnel.

According to Roberts and Levison findings suggest that officers took their job stress home and it influenced their interactions with their wives. These influences of job stress were found regardless of couples' marital satisfaction, the husband's work shift and the couple's parenthood status. They further claim that job stress is far more toxic for marital interaction than is physical exhaustion. A husband's job stress produces a physiological and affective climate in which both spouses show many of the signs associated with future marital dissolution and distress like heightened cardiovascular arousal, increased negative affect decreased positive affect and more emotional

distance and disconnectedness. Even with those who attempt to leave their stress at work or keep their lingering stress to themselves, stress is likely to have a pernicious effect on the emotional balance of marital interactions. It is also important to keep in mind that marital discord appears to be the most significant problem for the suicidal officer.

Additional police stressors that appear to further contribute to marital discord include the following:

- **Overprotection of family members:** Due to the suspicious nature of the work and the trauma and degradation they observe daily, officers often become overly protective of their families, which can lead to resentment by the family members.
- **Problems with children:** Children of the police personnel often say that their father/mother never gives them proper time, love & care because of they were always have a tight busy schedule.
- **Hardening of emotions:** To function adequately on the job, officers often find it necessary to suppress their feelings, which can lead to conflicts with spouses due to communication problems.
- **Sexual problems:** The pressures and working hours of police work may lead to intimacy problems, which, in turn, lead to frustration and anxiety; this lack of intimacy may then lead the parties to seek release outside the marriage. Because marital and family problems can have such a devastating impact on job performance, many police departments are trying to help their officers in reducing their problems by developing programs aimed at helping family members to understand and cope with the stressors inherent in police work

Occupational stress

Occupational stress is psychological stress related to one's job. Occupational stress refers to a chronic condition. Occupational stress can be managed by understanding what the stressful conditions at work are and taking steps to remediate those conditions. Occupational stress can occur when workers do not feel supported by supervisors or coworkers, feel as if they have little control over the work they perform, or find that their efforts on the job are incommensurate with the job's rewards. Occupational stress is a concern for both employees and employers because stressful job conditions are related to employees' emotional well-being, physical health, and job performance. A landmark study conducted by the World Health Organization and the International Labor Organization found that exposure to long working hours, which are theorized to operate through increased psycho-social occupational stress, is the occupational risk factor with the largest attributable burden of disease, according to these official estimates causing an estimated 745,000 workers to die from ischemic heart disease and stroke events in 2016.

Psychological theories of worker stress

A number of psychological theory at least partly explain the occurrence of occupational stress. The theories include the demand-control-support model, the effort-reward imbalance model, the person-environment fit model, job characteristics model, the diathesis stress model, and the job-demands resources model.

1. Demand-control-support model
2. Effort-reward imbalance model
3. Person–environment fit model
4. Job characteristics model
5. Job demands-resources model

Signs and symptoms of excessive job and workplace stress:

Signs and symptoms of excessive job and workplace stress include

1. Anxiety
2. Depressed mood
3. Irritability
4. Apathy, loss of interest in work
5. Problems sleeping
6. Fatigue
7. Trouble concentrating
8. Muscle tension
9. Headaches
10. Stomach problems
11. Social withdrawal
12. Loss of sex drive
13. Excessive use alcohol or drugs.

Burnout

It happens to everyone at some point or another. Our lives get busy going here and there working, helping others, or taking care of our families. Sometimes, we get too busy and forget to take a step back and rest. That is when burnout can occur. Burnout is a form of exhaustion caused by constantly feeling swamped. It's a result of excessive and prolonged emotional, physical, and mental stress. In many cases, burnout is related to one's job. Burnout happens when you're overwhelmed, emotionally drained, and unable to keep up with life's incessant demands. The condition isn't medically diagnosed. But burnout can affect your physical and mental health if you don't acknowledge or treat it. Burnout keeps you from being productive. It reduces your energy, making you feel hopeless,

cynical, and resentful. The effects of burnout can hurt your home, work, and social life. Long-term burnout can make you more vulnerable to cold and flues.

Major reasons for burnout include:

1. Unmanageable workloads
2. Unfair treatment at work
3. Confusing work responsibilities
4. Lack of communication or support from managers
5. Immense deadline pressure

Types of Burnout

Three types of burnout have been identified, each with their own cause:

Overload Burnout

This happens when you work harder and harder, becoming frantic in your pursuit of success. If you experience this, you may be willing to risk your health and personal life to feel successful in your job.

Under-Challenged Burnout

This happens when you feel underappreciated and bored in your job. Maybe your job doesn't provide learning opportunities or have room for professional growth. If you feel under-challenged, you may distance yourself from your job, become cynical, and avoid responsibilities

Neglect Burnout

This happens when you feel helpless at work. If things aren't going right, you may believe you're incompetent or unable to keep up with your responsibilities. Such burnout can be closely connected to imposter syndrome, a psychological pattern in which you doubt your skills, talents, or accomplishments.

Signs of Burnout

Burnout doesn't happen immediately. It's a gradual process that builds with stressors from your job. Signs and symptoms can be subtle at first. But the longer they go unaddressed, the worse they can become, which can lead to a breakdown. Burnout can have many symptoms. It can often be confused with stress or escalate into depression. These are signs to look for if you or someone close to you is experiencing burnout:

Exhaustion

You may feel drained and unable emotionally to deal with problems around you, both professional and personal. You may experience extreme tiredness and low feelings, leaving you without energy. These symptoms can show themselves in physical pain, stomach, or bowel problems.

Alienation from Activities

Look out for signs of cynicism and frustration toward work and colleagues. You may start to distance yourself emotionally, feeling numb about your work and environment.

Reduced Performance

This can occur at work, home, or when caring for family members because you have no energy left for everyday tasks. Burnout makes it hard to concentrate, handle responsibilities, or be creative.

Review of literature

In conclusion, the objective of this study was to determine whether there is a statistical significant correlation between an officer's emotional intelligence and burnout levels. The reason was that emotional intelligence is an important resource that supports employees in their efforts to cope with emotional and time demands of their service work as well as with states of emotional dissonance (Giardini & Frese, 2006).

Officers are considered to be at high risk for burnout due to the nature of police work. The skills that a police officer needs to demonstrate includes the ability to decide quickly and accurately, the ability to favorably interact with the community and to observe, retain and recall detailed information. However, these skills are affected when the officer experiences feelings of stress and burnout (Goodman, 1990). One variable that might help officers with these skills is emotional intelligence (Levert, et. al., 2000; Mayer & Salovey, 1997). Farmer (2004) suggests if emotional intelligence has a negative relationship with burnout, it is essential for individuals to develop or enhance their emotional intelligence, as high emotional intelligence would be regarded as a resistance to burnout. This would also mean that individuals with high emotional intelligence, having the ability to perceive, use, understand and manage emotions would be less likely to experience burnout as evident by the current study. The current study's findings are congruent with Slaski and Cartwright (2003). They proposed emotional intelligence could serve as a moderator in the stress process that precedes burnout. In this study that was not the purpose. However support was found in that individuals with high emotional intelligence will perceive work experiences as less stressful, have health consequences and thus will possess the ability to effectively cope with environmental demands (Bar-On, 1997a). Since officers believe that they are emotionally intelligent, they would be expected to be emotionally prepared in dealing effectively with stressful police work and thus, are likely to experience less burnout.

Regarding the dimensions of the burnout construct, it was the emotional exhaustion factor that appeared as a predictor of psychological health. Considering this, it

is necessary to mention that other studies have also indicated similar results in police officers (Gayman and Bradley, 2013; White et al., 2015). Regarding the dimensions of the hardy personality, it was the challenge factor that was introduced as a predictor within the regression model. Resilience is considered by most researchers as a significant construct in the study of health (Hystad et al., 2011). Likewise, hardy personality is a predictor of burnout. In countries such as Portugal, a longitudinal study conducted by Garrosa et al. (2010) with a sample of 98 nurses also confirmed that the control and challenge dimensions of the hardy personality had a specific contribution as negative predictors in the development of burnout.

As for the strengths of this research, it offers results on both of the organizational and personal variables, which have been jointly taken into account for the purpose of identifying which of these factors predicted a higher frequency of symptoms related to perception of worse mental health in police officers. On the contrary, the results presented serve to improve intervention practices for work-related stress in police officers. It has been observed in this study that the perception of problems and difficult situations as challenges or emotionally exhausting factors predict mental health; therefore, interventions for occupational stress to improve psychological health in these professionals should be addressed to those factors. The results of this research are somehow expected, since a main role has always been given to the variable – control over work – and, in this case, it does not appear as a predictor of mental health. In the same way, it is necessary to mention the different limitations of this research. In the first place, this is a cross-sectional design, which makes it impossible to obtain causal relations. On the contrary, the difficulty to access this sample, in many cases prevents longitudinal studies that provide information obtained over time (Sánchez-Teruel and Robles, 2014).

In general, the adverse perception of psychosocial risk factors was associated with high levels of emotional exhaustion and depersonalization. Among the perception of the psychosocial risk factors, the results found agree that other studies that suggest that police officers feel stressed and they perceived excessive demands in their work (Guet al., 2015). The fact that the police officers of the present research perceived these work conditions in an adverse way can be related to the tasks included in this role, since it is one of the most stressful professions (Campbell and Nobel, 2009). They are obliged to carry firearms, which represents the reason why these workers are susceptible to suffer situations of risk in which themselves or third parties are involved. Such situations generate stress and produce psychological distress (Vilardell et al., 2014).

Objectives

1. To examine the relationship of occupational stress and burnout among police constables.
2. To examine the relative importance of various Occupational stressors predicting the burnout.
3. To examine the relationship between various affected related abilities of traits associated with Occupational Stressors Burnout.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses have been formulated in this paper:

1. Male Police Constable and Female Police Constable would not differ significantly in term of burnout.
2. Male Police Constable and Female Police Constable would not differ significantly in term of occupational stress.

Methodology

Sample: the sample of the study will consist of 25 males and 25 female police constables of the age range of 30 to 55 years who will be selected from Varanasi districts to cover board demographic areas. These police constables will be selected by the purposive sampling technique. Following inclusion and exclusion criteria will be adopted to make the group more homogeneous.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Only those police constables with minimum job experience of five years.
2. Age range between 30 to 55 years.

Exclusion criteria:

Any history of Psychiatry, psychosomatic or internist disorders. A control group of 25 males and 25 females of the same age range and education will also be included in the sample. They should not have any history of psychiatric or psychosomatic problem and they should possess normal physical health.

Research Design

The study will be planned with 2x2 factorial designs and Multiple regressions. There will be two groups (Police Constables and Control Group) and two genders (Male and Female).

Tools

The multi-dimensional emotional intelligence scale-

Revised (MSREIS-R, Pandey and Anand;(2008)- to assess the emotional intelligence of the participants the MSRIES-R (Pandey and Anand 2008) was used. This scale consists of 56 items related to four dimension of emotional intelligence namely ability to perceive emotion (18 items), ability to utilize emotion (18

items), ability to express emotion (9 items), and ability to manage emotion (11 items). The participants were asked first to decide whether they agree or disagree with the statement and then they are asked to describe the intensity of their agreement or disagreement on a 3- point scale ranging from 1 very much to 3 to some extent. Finally, the ratings are converted to 6-point scale ranging from 1 to 6.

Burnout Inventory by K. S. Mishra (2012).

This inventory consists 48 items divided into eight areas-

- I. Non-accomplishment,
- II. Depersonalization,
- III. Emotional exhaustion,
- IV. Friction,
- V. Task avoidance,
- VI. Distancing,
- VII. Neglecting
- VIII. Easy going.

It was administered on Teachers Working in Higher Education

Institution and Students of B.Ed. Courses.

RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1: Presenting the Mean, SD, N and t value of Male Police Constable and Female Police Constable on occupational stress.

Groups	N	Mean	SD	t value
Male Police Constable	25	115	23.25	0.80
Female Police Constable	25	111	21.02	21.02

Table 1 presents the N mean SD and t value of Male Police Constable and Female Police Constable on occupational stress. It is clear from the above table that Male scored higher mean (mean=115) on occupational stress as compared to their counterpart Female mean (mean=111). Their SDs are 23.25 and 21.02 respectively. That t value 0.08 clearly shows that both groups not significantly differ on them level of occupational stress. Thus, null hypothesis "Male Police Constable and Female Police Constable would not differ significantly in term of occupational stress" not to be rejected.

Table 2: Presenting the Mean, SD, N and t value of MALE and FEMALE on burnout.

Groups	N	Mean	SD
MALE Police Constables	25	71	11.02
FEMALE Police Constables	25	72	11.98

Table 2 shows the N mean SD and t value of MALE Police Constable and FEMALE Police Constable on burnout. It is clear from the above table that Female scored higher mean (mean=72) on burnout as compared to their counterpart Male mean (mean=71). Their SDs are 11.02 and 11.98 respectively. The t value 0.38 clearly shows that both groups not significantly differ on their level of occupational stress. Thus, null hypothesis "Male Police Constable and Female Police Constable would not differ significantly in term of burnout" not to be rejected.

Table 3: Presenting the correlation coefficient between occupational stress and burnout among different sample subgroups (Male Police Constable and Female Police Constable). N=25 each

Groups	Occupational stress	
Burnout Constable	.61	Male Police Constable
Burnout Constable	.58	Female Police Constable

Table 3 clearly shows the correlation between occupational stress and burnout among the two groups namely Male Police Constable and Female Police Constable. It is evident from the table that occupational stress and burnout positively and significantly correlate with each other among Male Police Constable. Among Female Police Constable both variables namely occupational stress and burn out positively and significantly correlated with each other occupational stress and burnout significantly and positively associated with each other.

CONCLUSION

1. Male Police Constable and Female Police Constable not differ significantly in term of burnout.
2. Male Police Constable and Female Police Constable not differ significantly in term of occupational stress.
3. There is significant and positively relationship between occupational stress and burnout among Male Police Constable.

4. There is significant and positive relationship between burnout and occupational stress among Female Police Constable.
5. There is significant and positive relationship between occupational stress and burnout among Male Police Constable.

Suggestions for Future Research for future research following suggestions are suggested:

Increase the sample size so that the results can be generalized confidentially.

Samples from other districts should be included for future study.

The both variables should and must be study with personality and coping mechanism.

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